

CEPHIA

*Consortium for the Evaluation and
Performance of HIV Incidence Assays*

Ortho Less Sensitive (LS)-VITROS ECI

Evaluation Report

**Blood Systems
Research Institute**

**Public Health
England**

**BILL & MELINDA
GATES foundation**

UCSF

University of California
San Francisco

advancing health worldwide™

SACEMA

DST/NRF Centre of Excellence in Epidemiological Modelling and Analysis

Evaluation of Ortho Less Sensitive (LS)-VITROS ECI

Less Sensitive Modified VITROS Enzyme Immunoassay

CEPHIA PROJECT TEAM

**Gary Murphy¹ | Mike Busch² | Chris Pilcher³ | Alex Welte⁴
Elaine McKinney¹ | Sheila Keating² | Shelley Facente³
Reshma Kassanjee⁴**

1. PHE – Public Health England, Microbiology Services, Colindale, London, UK
2. BSRI - Blood Systems Research Institute, San Francisco
3. UCSF – University of California, San Francisco
4. SACEMA - South African Centre for Epidemiological Modelling and Analysis

Table of Contents

Summary	4
Background	5
CEPHIA	5
Introduction	6
Ortho Less Sensitive (LS)-VITROS ECI	7
Description of Assay	7
Summary and explanation of test	7
Principles of the procedure	9
Table 1 Assay information Summary	10
Evaluation panel and method	12
Analysis of Assay Characteristics	19
Definition of assay characteristics	19
Data analysis methods	20
Results	23
Conclusions and Recommendations	33
Technical Appraisal	34
Assay kits and reagents	34
Assay Preparation	34
Associated documents	35
Technical conclusions	35
Target Product Profile performance	37
Acknowledgements	39
References	40
Appendix - Evaluation Protocol	41
CEPHIA project management contact details	43
Manufacturer's comments	44
Enquires	44

Summary

Background

Monitoring the prevalence of HIV provides a blunt tool for understanding both recent transmission rates and the impact of behavioural changes or public health interventions on these rates. Consequently, there has been increasing application of assays, which are able to distinguish between ‘recently’ acquired HIV-1 infections and ‘long-standing’ infections, in cross-sectional surveys, to estimate HIV incidence. A comparative analysis of these existing incidence assays is a logical and necessary next step to facilitate the introduction of HIV incidence assays into wide use. In this assay, the LS-Vitros ECi, we are using the test off label and with a modified specimen. The results presented here relate to the performance of the assay in a modified format and do not relate to the licensed HIV diagnostic assay.

Evaluation Panel

The ‘evaluation panel’ consists of 2,500 uniquely-labelled HIV+ plasma specimens obtained from 928 distinct subjects, and was provided in 5 sets of 500 specimens each. 75 of these specimens represent 25 aliquots of each of 3 underlying specimens, and acted as (unmarked) controls. Laboratories were blinded to the specimen background information.

Data Analysis

The assay characteristics, namely the mean duration of recent infection (MDRI – average time ‘recent’ while infected for less than some time T) and false-recent rate (FRR – probability of a ‘recent’ result for an individual infected for longer than T), were estimated in a number of specimen sets. The MDRI (excluding treated subjects and identified elite controllers) is 306 days (95% CI: 274-338), for $T=2$ years and a Western blot HIV diagnostic test. The FRR in this specimen set is 10% (95% CI: 7-14%). High FRRs occur amongst treated subjects (>70%), elite controllers (>45%) and virally suppressed subjects (>60%).

Technical Appraisal

This assay is widely available 3rd generation, antibody only, assay performed on an automated platform. It requires a stable electrical mains supply but no additional electrical works. The platform can be used for a number of other assays and requires user and manufacturer maintenance to ensure optimal performance. The assay is simple to perform as it only requires a 1:400 dilution of the specimen in Ortho Diluent Buffer B before testing following which all remaining steps are performed on-board the platform. The use of the automated platform ensures that the assay is very reproducible. There is no EQA programme for the modified assay nor analysis software for the modified format thus there is a possibility of operator error in avidity calculations.

Conclusions

This does not reach the Target Product Profile (TPP) for use in cross sectional incidence assays and we do not recommend its use.

Background

In recent years it has become recognized that monitoring of the current burden, or prevalence, of HIV infection in populations is a blunt tool for understanding both recent transmission trends and the impact of behavioural change and public health interventions on those trends. Tests able to distinguish recently-acquired HIV-1 infections from long-standing ones by testing a single serum specimen from an infected individual, and by applying them to cross-sectional serosurveys to estimate population incidence rates, are being increasingly used. The term RITA (Recent Infection Test Algorithm) has been coined to describe assays and combinations of assays and other (clinical) criteria that are able to identify recent HIV infection. While any of several assays may be used within a RITA, each of them is dependent first and foremost on employing highly sensitive methods to detect and confirm the presence of anti- HIV-1 antibodies in the specimen. A method is then employed whose signal takes considerably longer to exceed a threshold above which the specimen is considered to be from a long-standing infection. The methods rely on the generalisation that the signal measured increases gradually, and at a similar rate, in each infected individual, over a period of several months following primary HIV infection and seroconversion

It has been recognized at various meetings of the WHO Technical Working Group on Incidence Assays that a statistically sound comparative analysis of existing incidence assays is a logical and necessary next step to facilitate the introduction of HIV incidence assays into wide use. In 2011, The Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation funded a project '*Development of specimen repository and evaluation of assays for identification of recent HIV infection and estimation of HIV incidence*' to help facilitate this aim.

CEPHIA

The **Consortium for the Evaluation and Performance of HIV Incidence Assays** (CEPHIA) brings together world leaders in the development, performance and application of RITA assays that are able to identify recent HIV infection. CEPHIA's purpose is to successfully deliver the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation funded project and to advance the understanding of currently available assays that can identify recent HIV infection; to better describe the duration of the infection state in which they identify recent infection; and to determine the rate at which they misclassify specimens as from recent infections.

Specific project objectives are to evaluate and compare currently available assays for use in the measurement of recent HIV infection using a common set of specimens collected for this purpose and to assess the ability of the assays, alone or in combination, to accurately estimate HIV incidence in populations.

An overview of CEPHIA, related documentation and updates is available at <http://www.incidence-estimation.org/page/cephia-overview>

Appendix 2 details CEPHIA Group members

Introduction

As part of the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation funded project, *'Development of specimen repository and evaluation of assays for identification of recent HIV infection and estimation of HIV incidence'*, the CEPHIA group undertook assessments of a number of available assays. This report details the results of the characterisation of the Ortho Avidity-VITROS assay.

A CEPHIA 'qualification panel' of specimens was used for preliminary assessment of the assay's potential for determining HIV recency, before a full assessment was undertaken using an 'evaluation panel' of specimens. Qualification panel testing was performed by Blood Systems Research Institute (BSRI), San Francisco, California, USA. The results of this analysis are discussed in *'The performance of candidate assays to detect recent HIV infection for cross-sectional incidence estimation: an independent, comparative evaluation'*. Poster 1056, *20th Conference on Retroviruses and Opportunistic Infections* [2].

Full assessment of the Ortho LS-VITROS was considered justified based on review of the qualification panel analysis by the CEPHIA management team. The evaluation panel testing was performed at BSRI.

The 2,500 HIV-1 positive plasma specimens used for the evaluation were sourced by the CEPHIA team at the University of California San Francisco (UCSF), USA and comprised a wide range of suitable and challenging specimen types.

All evaluation panel data was analysed by the CEPHIA team at the South African Centre for Epidemiological Modelling and Analysis (SACEMA), Stellenbosch, South Africa.

This evaluation aims to advance the understanding and performance of currently available assays, and to better describe the duration of time for which assays classify infections as 'recently' acquired and the rate at which they (mis)classify infections of long-infected subjects as 'recent'. The reported analysis below focuses on estimation of the characteristics of the incidence assay, namely the mean duration of recent infection (MDRI - average time spent 'recently' infected) and false-recent rate (FRR - proportion of long-infected subjects who are classified as 'recently' infected), for various subpopulations. Standard operating procedures for, and experiences in, the laboratory application of the incidence assay are also discussed.

Ortho Less-Sensitive (LS)-VITROS Assay Information

Description of Assay

In its licensed form, the **VITROS ECi/ECiQ Immunodiagnostic System** is currently being used for the *in vitro* qualitative detection of antibodies to Human Immunodeficiency Virus types 1 and/or 2 (anti-HIV-1 and anti-HIV-2) in human serum and plasma (heparin, EDTA or citrate). The results of the VITROS Anti-HIV 1+2 assay, in conjunction with other serological evidence and clinical information, may be used as an aid in the diagnosis of infection with HIV-1 and/or HIV-2 in persons with signs or symptoms of, or at risk for, HIV infection.

Potentially, after identification of an HIV positive specimen, the same specimen can be reflexed to a recency assay. By including a sample dilution, the length of time for detecting the evolution of HIV-1 antibodies is extended. This allows conversion of the VITROS HIV diagnostic assay to an HIV incidence assay. The assay identifies samples that are still within the seroconversion period and therefore considered recent infection. The time it takes for an individual to move from sensitive HIV assay positive to detuned HIV assay negative is the period of recency. Understanding the number of longstanding infections compared to recent infections over a period of time studied will enable calculations of incidence of HIV in a population. Currently, these assays are not used for clinical diagnostic purposes.

Summary and explanation of the test

While no modifications have been made to the performance of the assay on the clinical diagnostic system, we have modified the sample with dilution and a chaotropic agent before placing the sample on the VITROS system. The samples are run through the HIV diagnostic assay according to the protocol established in the HIV-1/2 protocol card. The test result is calculated by looking at the ratio of the HIV antibody that is washed away with the 1:400 dilution in Ortho Clinical Diagnostics Dilution Buffer B. The VITROS Anti-HIV 1+2 assay is performed using the VITROS Immunodiagnostic Products Anti-HIV 1+2 Reagent Pack and the VITROS Immunodiagnostic Products Anti-HIV 1+2 calibrator on the VITROS ECi/ECiQ Immunodiagnostic System. An immunometric bridging technique is used; this involves a two-stage reaction. In the first stage HIV antibody present in the sample binds with HIV recombinant antigen coated on the wells. Unbound sample is removed by washing. In the second stage horseradish peroxidase (HRP)-labelled recombinant HIV antigens are added in the conjugate reagent. The conjugate binds specifically to any human anti-HIV-1 or anti-HIV-2 (IgG and IgM) captured on the well in the first stage. Unbound conjugate is removed by washing. The bound HRP conjugate is measured by a luminescent reaction. A reagent containing luminogenic substrate called the Signal reagent is added to the wells. The light signals are read by the VITROS ECi/ECiQ Immunodiagnostic System. The amount of HRP conjugate bound is indicative of the level of anti-HIV 1 and anti-HIV-2 present

This assay contains four recombinant antigens (HIV-1 Env 13, HIV-1 Env 10, HIV-1 p24, and HIV-2 Env AL) derived from HIV-1 core, HIV-1 envelope and HIV-2 envelope.

- HIV-1 Env 13, envelope SOD fusion protein, contains regions from both gp 120 and gp 41 regions.
- HIV-1 Env 10, envelope SOD fusion protein, contains a gp41 region which extends beyond the C-terminus of Env 13.

- HIV-1 p24 is derived from full length core protein of HIV-1.
- HIV-2 Env AL, envelope SOD fusion protein, contains a region from gp 36 of HIV-2.

These antigens detect antibodies to HIV-1 and antibodies to HIV-2 in the same test. Results are calculated as a normalized signal, relative to a calibrator cutoff value. During the calibration process, a lot-specific parameter, encoded on the lot calibration card, is used to determine a valid stored cutoff value for the VITROS ECi/ECiQ Immunodiagnostic System and results are given as Signal/Cutoff (S/C).

These antigens detect antibodies to HIV-1 and antibodies to HIV-2 in the same test. Results are calculated as a normalized signal, relative to a calibrator cut-off value. During the calibration process, a lot-specific parameter, encoded on the lot calibration card, is used to determine a valid stored cut-off value for the VITROS ECi/ECiQ Immunodiagnostic System and results are given as Signal/Cut-off (S/C).

The optimized version of the LS-VITROS assay uses a 1:400 dilution of HIV-positive samples in dilution buffer, with the assay screening in single and confirmed in duplicate. In the early stages of LS-modified assay development, the dilution of the HIV-positive plasma sample in dilution buffer B was prepared using a two-step (1:20 and 1:20) manual dilution. However, automation of this step is possible by transferring this dilution step on-board the VITROS platform after further development of system programming. After samples are diluted, the fully automated VITROS ECi robot takes 49 minutes to run the each sample in the assay and to report the results as signal to cutoff (S/C) values. The VITROS ECi has the capacity to run 70 samples per hour while newer models have much higher throughput. Using samples previously tested by Vironostika, we identified potential S/C values for optimal discrimination of recent infection.

Principles of the procedure

PRINCIPLES OF THE PROCEDURE

Protocol Step	Reaction
80 µl sample	Sample added first due to system requirement. Large sample volume required in order to achieve high sensitivity.
20 µl Assay Reagent	Adds components to minimize differences between serum and plasma samples and prevent binding of yeast reactive samples.
Incubate at 37 °C 29min 20sec	Reaction is accelerated by high temperature. Anti-HIV 1+2 in the sample binds to the recombinant HIV antigens on the plate
Wash	Removes unbound material.
100µl Conjugate Reagent	Adds the four conjugated recombinant HIV antigens.
Incubate at 37 °C 8min	Reaction is accelerated by high temperature. Conjugated recombinant antigens bind to any specific anti-HIV 1+2 immobilised on the plate during the first incubation
Wash	Removes unbound material.
Add 200 µl SR	Horseshradish peroxidase in bound conjugate catalyses the chemiluminescent reaction
Read	Signal read at fixed time after Signal Reagent addition and used to determine the result from the assay Cut-off.

Table 1: Assay Information Summary

General	
Assay Name	Ortho Avidity VITROS Assay
Manufacturer	Ortho Clinical Diagnostics
Catalogue Number	See below
Number of Specimens can test/Kit – Screen mode	100 tests
Test Volume – Screen mode	180uL in sample cup of 1:10 dilution of sample to dilution or guanidine (20uL sample per cup)
Presentation	
Assay type	Enzyme Immunoassay
Conjugate	Horse Radish Peroxidase (HRP)
Substrate	Signal Reagent
Stop Solution	None
Reading wavelength	Chemiluminescent
Calibrator (CAL)	The assay calibrator is run and used to set the cut-off values at the start of a lot. The Signal to Cut-off is calculated by dividing the fluorescence intensity (FI) value of the sample by the FI of the calibrator and multiplication by a converter to normalize the calibrator. This calculation is done by the VITROS software and the results are reported as signal to cut-off (SCO)
Internal (Ortho) Controls User defined controls – For this evaluation we used control material supplied by Bio-Rad	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ortho Negative control (HIV, HB, HCV negative) [NC x 2] - Ortho HIV-1 Control [VPC1x 2] - Ortho HIV-2 Control [VPC2x2] - Bio-Rad Negative Control [BNCx2] - Bio-Rad HIV-1 Control [BPC1x2] - Bio-Rad HIV-2 Control [BPC2x2]
Stages	
Specimen Pre-dilution set-up time	30 minutes
Sample/Conjugate/Substrate incubations	Performed by automated system.
Total time to completion	50 minutes from set-up to results.

Equipment and Reagents Required	
Diluent Buffer B	Ortho Clinical Diagnostics Supplied
High and Low Avidity Controls	Internal controls: External Control: Bio-Rad HIV-1 positive, HIV-1 negative – user may define own controls.
Pipettes	20 uL, 200 uL single and multi- channel, tips
Ortho Clinical Diagnostics Vitros 5600 Eci, plus software	Contact Ortho Clinical Diagnostics
OCD Universal Sample Tray, 10 slot	Contact Ortho Clinical Diagnostics
Calibrator Anti HIV-1 plus 2	6801862
Reagent anti HIV-1+2 100PIECES/BX 1BX/1EA	6801861
Universal Wash Reagent	8389793
Vitros Versa Tips	6801715
Vitros Micro Sample Cups	1213115
Universal Wash Reagent	8389793
E & K Scientific Titer Tubes	604508
OCD Vitros Signal Reagent	1072693
OCD Reagent Pack Anti HIV 1 & 2	6801861

Evaluation Panel and Method

The 'evaluation panel' consists of 2,500 uniquely-labelled HIV+ plasma specimens obtained from 928 distinct subjects, and was provided to laboratories in 5 sets of 500 specimens each. 75 of these specimens represent 25 aliquots of each of 3 underlying specimens, and acted as (unmarked) controls. Laboratory technicians were blinded to the specimen background information.

Evaluation panel testing is intended to provide the relevant data to estimate assay characteristics, assess and compare assay performance, and optimize the algorithms of assays and biomarkers used in RITAs, for purposes of estimating HIV incidence.

Tables 2 to 6, and Figure 1, describe the sources and characteristics of specimens included in the evaluation panel.

The CEPHIA Evaluation Panel was tested by Ortho LS-VITROS Assay EIA following the CEPHIA SOP (Document 19A).

Prior to beginning the evaluation the evaluator(s) received training from manufacturer on how to operate the VITROS ECI Immunodiagnostic system.

The evaluation was conducted under the strict quality requirements as laid out in the CEPHIA Quality Management Strategy (Document 002). Refer to Appendix 1 – Evaluation Protocol for further details.

KIT LOTS USED: Lot 540

STORAGE OF ASSAY KITS: Stored at 4°C before using. The kit is maintained at 4°C after being loaded onto the Diagnostic System.

All equipment had undergone proper installation, operation and performance/monitoring qualification prior to testing to minimise assay variability.

The standard operating procedures for Evaluation Panel testing are available on the project website (<http://www.incidence-estimation.com/page/cephia>)[1].

Table 2: Source of Specimens used in the Evaluation Set

Type of partner site	Site Name	Location of specimen draws
Seroconverter Cohorts		
<i>US and Brazil cohorts enrol subjects diagnosed with acute HIV seroconversion.</i>	UCSF Options Project UCSD Acute HIV Study AMPLIAR	San Francisco San Diego Brazil
<i>IAVI Protocol C enrolls subjects who seroconvert during participation in an HIV incidence cohort study.</i>	IAVI Protocol C	Kenya Rwanda Uganda
<i>All cohorts follow subjects both prior to and after antiretroviral therapy.</i>		South Africa Zambia
HIV positive cohorts		
<i>SCOPE enrolls HIV positive men and women both on and off ARV treatment, actively recruits elite controllers, and follows these subjects over time.</i>	SCOPE San Francisco Men’s Health Study (SFMHS)	San Francisco
<i>SFMHS enrolled both HIV negative and HIV positive men from a population-based sample in SF and followed these subjects forward over time.</i>		
Blood Banks		
<i>Blood banks identify repeat blood donors with a negative blood donation followed by a subsequent HIV positive donation.</i>	American Red Cross Blood Centers of the Pacific South Africa National Blood Services (SANBS) Hemocentro do Sao Paulo	United States South Africa Brazil

Table 3: Demographic / infection characteristics of subjects contributing specimens to the evaluation panel

Subject/ specimen group	Number of subjects (% of subjects)	Number of specimens (% of specimens)
All subjects	928 (100)	2500 (100)
Gender		
Male	728 (78)	1872 (75)
Female	194 (21)	547 (22)
Country of specimen draws		
USA	523 (56)	1298 (52)
Zambia	166 (18)	508 (20)
Rwanda	65 (7)	281 (11)
Uganda	62 (7)	200 (8)
Brazil	18 (2)	85 (3)
South Africa	58 (6)	64 (3)
Kenya	36 (4)	63 (3)
Age at draw (years)		
<20	28 (3)	49 (2)
20-30	231 (25)	566 (23)
30-40	357 (38)	887 (35)
40-50	270 (29)	635 (25)
50-60	92 (10)	240 (10)
>60	21 (2)	45 (2)
HIV Subtype ¹		
B	525 (57)	1247 (50)
C	250 (27)	670 (27)
A1	92 (10)	290 (12)
D	42 (5)	157 (6)
Other	19 (2)	135 (5)

¹ 42% of subjects (capturing 52% of specimens) had their infection subtypes confirmed through laboratory testing, while the remainder of subtypes were based on the majority subtype in country of specimen draw.

Figure 1: Number of specimens drawn over time per subject, for specimens included on the evaluation panel

Table 4: Times from (estimated) infection to specimen draws for ARV-naïve subjects included in the evaluation panel (for estimation of the MDRI), stratified by HIV-1 subtype¹

	All subtypes	Subtype B	Subtype C	Subtype A1	Subtype D
Subject/ specimen group	Number of subjects				
Subject has estimable infection date ²	422	104	185	83	38
<1 year duration of infection (DOI) at specimen draw	283	59	145	39	33
1-2 years DOI	224	39	105	54	19
2-3 years DOI	125	22	56	34	11
3-4 years DOI	72	15	33	19	4
4+ years DOI	41	14	19	7	0
Subject/ specimen group	Number of specimens				
Subject has estimable infection date ²	1386	344	588	263	149
<1 year duration of infection (DOI) at specimen draw	671	164	308	71	103
1-2 years DOI	346	70	146	93	27
2-3 years DOI	189	42	72	58	14
3-4 years DOI	104	28	40	29	4
4+ years DOI	66	34	20	11	0

¹ Elite controllers (defined in *Analysis of Assay Characteristics*) from SCOPE (see Table 2) are excluded as the study specifically recruited (untreated) subjects with sustained low HIV viral loads, and therefore data would otherwise be over-enriched with elite controllers.

² Infection refers to the time of positivity of Western blot. See *Analysis of Assay Characteristics* for the approach used for estimating infection times, and for identifying subjects with estimable infected times, for this particular analysis.

Table 5: Description of specimens from ARV-naïve long-infected subjects included in the evaluation panel (for estimation of the FRR), stratified by HIV-1 subtype¹

	All subtypes	Subtype B	Subtype C	Subtype A1	Subtype D
Subject/ specimen group	Number of subjects				
Subject infected for greater than 1 year ²	456	243	121	62	21
Subject infected for greater than 2 years ²	316	190	75	37	11
Subject infected for greater than 3 years ²	224	156	42	20	4
Subject infected for greater than 4 years ²	161	137	18	6	0
Subject infected for greater than 5 years ²	111	111	0	0	0
Subject/ specimen group	Number of specimens				
Subject infected for greater than 1 year ²	1112	538	297	210	47
Subject infected for greater than 2 years ²	665	388	144	106	18
Subject infected for greater than 3 years ²	416	301	63	43	4
Subject infected for greater than 4 years ²	285	256	19	10	0
Subject infected for greater than 5 years ²	192	192	0	0	0

¹ Elite controllers (defined in *Analysis of Assay Characteristics*) from SCOPE (see Table 2) are excluded as the study specifically recruited (untreated) subjects with sustained low HIV viral loads, and therefore data would otherwise be over-enriched with elite controllers.

² Specimen drawn at least 1, 2, 3, 4 or 5 years (see row labels) after a first recorded HIV-positive diagnosis.

Table 6: Description of *challenge* specimens drawn from subjects infected for greater than 2 years included in the evaluation panel (for estimation of the FRR)¹

Subject/ specimen group	All subtypes ²	
	Number of subjects	Number of specimens
SCOPE elite controllers ²	31	89
CD4 cell count < 200 at draw	124	214
Treated subjects ³	113	185
Treatment initiated within 6 months of infection	53	90
Treatment initiated 6-24 months after infection	17	28
Treatment initiated >24 months after infection	33	54
Viral load < 75 copies/ml	154	273

¹ 98% of subjects (or specimens) represent subtype B infections.

² Subjects were identified as elite controllers by SCOPE (classification rules are outlined in defined in *Analysis of Assay Characteristics*).

³ Treated for at least 3 months and without interruption.

Analysis of Assay Characteristics

The methods and results outlined below are reported in the following journal article: ‘Kassanjee R, Pilcher CD, Keating SM, Facente SN, McKinney E, Price MA, Martin JN, Little S, Hecht FM, Kallas EG, Welte A, Busch MP, Murphy G, on behalf of the *Consortium for the Evaluation and Performance of HIV Incidence Assays* (CEPHIA); Independent assessment of candidate HIV incidence assays on specimens in the CEPHIA repository [3].

Definitions of Assay Characteristics

In 1995, Brookmeyer and Quinn [4] introduced the concept of cross-sectional HIV incidence estimation: incidence can be measured from a single survey conducted a point in time using both (i) observed survey counts of HIV-negative, ‘recently’ infected and ‘non-recently’ infected subjects, and (ii) knowledge about the dynamics of the test for recent infection. However, the state of ‘recent’ infection demonstrated in their work (namely, detectability of p24 antigens in the absence of detectable HIV antibodies) occurs for only a few weeks after infection, resulting in unrealistically large surveys being required for precise incidence estimation. Subsequently, various tests, with more enduring states of ‘recent’ infection, have been proposed. However, the behaviour of currently available tests has been imperfect – due to inter-subject variability, a substantial proportion of long-infected individuals nevertheless return ‘recent’ results.

As the methodology has matured, a general theoretical framework has been derived, which consistently accounts for these ‘false-recent’ results [5]. Two test characteristics that summarise test dynamics emerge as required for purposes of incidence surveillance:

- the **mean duration of recent infection (MDRI)**, Ω_T , which is the average time spent alive and ‘recently’ infected, while infected for less than some time cut-off T , and
- the **false-recent rate (FRR)**, β_T , which is the probability that an individual who is infected for longer than T will return a ‘recent’ result.

This general framework was developed by introducing a post-infection time cut-off, T , to separate ‘true-recent’ from ‘false-recent’ results. In a cross-sectional survey, the estimate of incidence would be

$$\hat{I}_T = \frac{n_R - \hat{\beta}_T n_+}{n_S \cdot (\hat{\Omega}_T - \hat{\beta}_T T)},$$

where n_+ and $n_S = n - n_+$ are the counts of HIV-positive and HIV-negative (or susceptible) subjects in the survey, n_R is the number of ‘recently’ infected subjects in the survey, and $\hat{\Omega}_T$ and $\hat{\beta}_T$ are the estimated MDRI and FRR for the test for recent infection respectively.

This analysis focuses on estimation of the MDRI and FRR. As the characteristics of incidence assays may vary across subpopulations, the characteristics are explored using various specimen sets.

Data Analysis Methods

Software. All data captured within CEPHIA are stored in a MySQL relational database. Database queries linked assay results to the background information on subjects and specimens for data analysis, which was then performed in Matlab (R2013b, the MathWorks Inc.).

Interpretation of assay results. The LS-Vitros results were interpreted according to developer's guidelines (see standard operating procedures on the CEPHIA project website [1]). In particular, a 'recent'/'non-recent' threshold of 20 was used to discriminate between 'recent' and 'non-recent' infection, with a measured signal-to-cut-off (S/C) of 20 or less interpreted as indicating 'recent' infection.

Stratification of data. Assay characteristics were estimated using specimen sets defined by stratifying on treatment history, viral load, CD4+ T cell count, time from infection to specimen draw, and HIV subtype (which was based on country of draw, for the 48% of specimens which lack explicit laboratory subtype confirmation). The characteristics of assays in 'elite controllers' (ECs), broadly defined as subjects who maintain undetectable or very low HIV viral loads without antiretroviral therapy (ART), is of particular interest. As the SCOPE study purposefully recruited ECs, this data was analysed separately. These subjects were ART-naïve (or without ART for at least 6 months), with all off-treatment viral load measurements (HIV-1 RNA) below 200 copies/ml and at least 50% of these measurements below 75 copies/ml.

Time cut-off T . The definitions of the MDRI and FRR rely on the previously mentioned construct of a post-infection time cut-off, T . If T is chosen to be too short, this limits the possible MDRI and typically raises the FRR. If T is chosen to be too long, it becomes difficult to obtain sufficient data to analyse the test dynamics with sufficient precision over this time after infection, and the MDRI will also develop variation by time and place (properties inevitable for the FRR) rather than capture stable biological properties of the test. A cut-off of $T = 2$ years is used throughout this work. The value of T was increased from 1 year, as used in preliminary analyses [2], to 2 years in this analysis, to better capture the tails of persisting 'recent' results and thus reduce FRRs.

Definition and estimation of infection times. In practice, the notion of 'infection' implicit in the assay characteristic definitions refers to 'detectable infection' – which depends on the particular HIV diagnostic test used in the incidence study. In this analysis, 'detectable infection' was defined as the time of seroconversion on an HIV viral lysate-based Western Blot assay. Based on the methodology summarised below, infection times were estimated for 56% of subjects.

The estimation of a subject's infection time relies on both data describing the subject's testing history and knowledge of the sensitivities of the various diagnostics tests used on the subject, where sensitivity captures the probability of detecting HIV in a (truly infected) subject as a function of time since detectability on the reference diagnostic test that is to be used in the incidence study (Western Blot in this case). In general, the formal likelihood of observing a subject's testing history can be directly generated as a function of time since

HIV infection (through vertical and horizontal inversion of the various diagnostic tests' sensitivity functions). Under prior assumptions about infection times, this likelihood function can then be used to produce an inferred posterior density function for possible infection times, which can then be used in analyses. Depending on available data, various simplifications of this estimation procedure could be considered.

For this analysis, infection times were estimated for subjects with available first HIV-positive test dates, Fiebig staging [6] information for first HIV-positive tests, and, at times, last HIV-negative test dates (within 120 days of first HIV-positive dates). The likelihood function for the infection time (corresponding to the time of entering Fiebig stage 5) of a subject was then calculated using the average durations of Fiebig stages presented in Lee et al [7] (neglecting inter-subject variability, assuming independence between diagnostic results for a subject, and making some assumptions about the types of diagnostics tests used at last HIV-negative test dates). A uniform prior for infection times was combined with the likelihood function, and the mean of the resulting posterior distribution for infection times provided a subject's estimated infection time, which was used in all subsequent analyses.

Efforts are currently being made to capture more detailed information on cohort-level diagnostic testing protocols and more complete testing histories of individual subjects, thus providing the required data to refine estimation of infection times for later analyses of assay results.

For subjects with unambiguous acute retroviral syndrome (ARS) symptoms onset dates between last HIV-negative and first HIV-positive test dates, infection was estimated to occur 17 days after ARS onset (based on the observation that the incubation period of ARS symptoms is about 14 days [8-11] and that the time from exposure to Western blot seroconversion averages 31 days [6,7]).

Estimation of MDRI. A number of methods can reasonably be used to estimate the MDRI, each with its own accuracy, precision and complexity – as explored in a separate, detailed benchmarking exercise (manuscript in preparation, by a working group operating on behalf of the HIV Modelling Consortium [12]). In this analysis, linear binomial regression, an approach found to be robust across a number of scenarios in this benchmarking project, and previously used for this purpose [13], has been applied. The model form is $g(P_R(t)) = f(t)$ where $P_R(t)$ is the probability of testing 'recent' at time t after infection, g is the chosen link function and $f(t)$ is a linear function of the model parameters, which are estimated by a maximum likelihood approach. Results from a 4-parameter model form are presented, where g is the logit link, and $f(t)$ is a cubic polynomial in t (Model A). Data points more than $1.1 \times T$ post infection were discarded before model fitting (Data Exclusion Rule I), with the aim of achieving the best fit of the model over $[0, T]$ post-infection, while avoiding diluting the data around the boundary at T . Sensitivity of results when increasing the data exclusion cut-off to $2 \times T$ (Data Exclusion Rule II) was also considered. Variation in results was explored when fitting two other model forms, namely (i) a more restrictive 2-parameter model where g is the log-log link and $f(t)$ is a linear function of $\ln(t)$ (Model B), and (ii) a flexible 7-parameter model where g is the logit link and $f(t)$ is a linear function of the natural cubic spline basis functions with interior knots occurring every 3 months after

infection, between 0 and T after infection (Model C). In all cases, the MDRI, expressed mathematically as $\int_0^T P_R(t)dt$, was estimated using the fitted $P_R(t) = g^{-1}(f(t))$.

To correctly account for the structure of the data, in the absence of explicit subject-level clustering in the fitted models, bootstrapping was performed by sampling subjects (not observations) with replacement. The 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of 10 000 MDRI estimate replicates provided 95% confidence interval (CI) limits [14].

Estimation of FRR. A population-level FRR is inherently dependent on the epidemiological and demographic history of a study population, and so a set of specimens, such as in the CEPHIA repository, can only be used to estimate the FRR in well-defined subpopulations. Therefore, specimens from long-infected subjects were identified (specimens drawn at least T after the subject's first recorded HIV-positive test time – adjusted to capture Western blot positivity), and the proportion of 'recently' infected subjects estimated in each of the specimen sets described above. To capture subject-level clustering, when a subject provided more than one result to any FRR estimate, the most frequent classification was used. When a subject had equal numbers of 'recent' and 'non-recent' classifications, the subject contributed 0.5 to the count of subjects who have a majority 'recent' classification. Exact Clopper-Pearson 95% CIs [15] are provided.

Reproducibility statistics. The sample mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation of the multiple assay measurements obtained for each of the unique reproducibility specimens, as well as each of the labelled quality controls, were also calculated.

Results

The incidence assay dynamics, excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers, are shown in Figures 2 to 4. The evolution of assay measurements by time since infection is shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3. In Figure 4, the proportion of 'recent' results (assay measurements below the 'recent'/'non-recent' threshold) is plotted by time since infection, also stratified by HIV subtype (B, C, D, and A1). The figures show that there is natural variability in biomarker maturation, leading to a significant number of subjects reaching the standard 'recent'/'non-recent' threshold more than one year after infection; and there is significant delay or failure to achieve maturation to 'non-recent' status among specimens of subtype A1.

The distribution of assay measurements for specimens drawn more than $T = 2$ years after infection is shown in Figure 5, for various specimen sets.

Figure 2: Spaghetti plot of subjects' assay measurements as a function of (estimated) time since infection (years), excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers

The figure represents 1376 data points from 418 subjects. The 'recent'/'non-recent' threshold is shown by a horizontal solid line.

Figure 3: Box-and-whisker plots of assay measurements as a function of (estimated) time since infection (years), excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers

The plot indicates percentiles of measurements in 6-monthly intervals of time after infection. The central 50% and median of measurements are captured by the box and dividing line respectively, and whiskers and markers capture remaining measurements and outliers respectively. There are 40-450 data points per group. The 'recent'/'non-recent' threshold is shown by the horizontal solid line.

Figure 4: The proportion of 'recent' results (%) as a function of (estimated) time since infection (years), excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers and stratifying by HIV subtype (B, C, D and A1)

Circles and lines show observed proportions and 95% confidence intervals respectively. Specimens are grouped into 6-monthly intervals of time since infection until 2 years, after which all specimens are grouped together. There are 25 to 665 data points per group, except for subtype D which has fewer than 20 points 1-2 years after infection.

A. All subtypes

B. Subtype B

C. Subtype C

D. Subtype D

E. Subtype A1

Figure 5: Empirical distribution of assay measurements for specimens drawn greater than $T = 2$ years after (estimated) infection time, by specimen set
 'Recent'/'non-recent' thresholds are shown by vertical solid lines.

A. Excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers

665 data points from 316 subjects.

B. Treated subjects

Treated for at least 3 months without interruption. 185 data points from 113 subjects.

C. SCOPE elite controllers

89 data points from 31 subjects.

D. Low viral load

Viral load < 75 copies/ml at draw. 273 data points from 154 subjects.

E. Low CD4+ T cell count

CD4 cell count < 200 cells/ μ l at draw. 214 data points from 124 subjects.

Table 7 provides estimated assay characteristics for various specimen sets. The estimated MDRI, excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers from the analysis, is 306 days (95% CI: 274-338). The result was insensitive (less than 3% change in result) to whether ARS symptoms onset dates were used to adjust estimated infection dates, a change to Data Exclusion Rule II, and the use of alternative Model C. The MDRI estimate increased by 3% when changing to Model B, which was the most sensitive to the data exclusion rules (6% increase in estimate when changing to Data Exclusion Rule II within Model B).

While characteristics have been estimated here on the standardized basis of a Western blot being used to identify HIV-positive subjects, other diagnostic screening tests are likely to be used in incidence studies, and the time between HIV exposure and reactivity on these tests can differ by several weeks [6,7,16]. Therefore, for application to incidence studies, the base case MDRI reported here would need to be increased or decreased – depending on the particular screening test or algorithm used in the study to classify a specimen as HIV-positive, and hence eligible for ‘recent’ infection testing.

The estimated FRRs provided in Table 7 are also plotted in Figure 6. Excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers, and analysing all remaining specimens drawn more than $T = 2$ years after infection, the measured FRR is 9.7% (95% CI: 6.6%-13.5%). When stratifying by time since infection, some persistence of ‘recent’ classifications is evident.

The FRR amongst elite controller specimens is high at 48% (95% CI: 30%-67%). The FRR amongst treated subjects is even higher, at 76% (95% CI: 67%-84%). Further stratifying treated subjects by time from infection to treatment initiation, the FRR decreases as the time to treatment initiation increases: for early treatment initiation (within 6 months of infection) the FRR is 93% (95% CI: 82%-98%), while for later treatment initiation (more than 6 months after infection) it is 57% (95% CI: 42% to 70%).

The FRR for subjects with low viral loads, here defined as below 75 copies/ml, is high, at 69% (95% CI: 61%-76%). This is consistent with results above, as 92% of this specimen set is made up of specimens from the identified elite controllers and treated subjects (and 94% of specimens from SCOPE elite controllers and treated subjects have a low viral load).

The FRR amongst subjects with low CD4+ T cell counts, namely less than 200 cells/ μ l and acting as a proxy for AIDS identification, was low at 2% (95% CI: 0%-7%).

Table 8 lists MDRI and FRR by subtype. Small p-values for pairwise subtype differences in the MDRI or FRRs involve subtype A1 (versus other subtypes). While these initial results highlight potential subtype differences and support further exploration of this topic, a more definitive analysis (beyond the present scope) should be performed – based on a large number of subtype D and A1 specimens and using estimation procedures specifically adapted to this stratification.

Table 7: Estimated assay characteristics (and 95% confidence intervals), for various specimen sets

Assay characteristics are estimated for $T = 2$ years and a context in which an HIV viral lysate-based Western blot assay is used to identify HIV-positive subjects in the incidence study.

	Number of subjects (number of data points)	Estimated assay characteristics (95% CI)
MDRI in days		
All specimens, excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers	400 (1032)	306 (274-338)
FRR as %		
All specimens, excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers	316 (665)	9.7 (6.6-13.5)
By time since infection (years), excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers		
(2,3]	140 (208)	17.5 (11.6-24.8)
(3,4]	77 (110)	14.9 (7.8-24.9)
(4,5]	35 (45)	5.7 (0.7-19.2)
>5	112 (193)	3.1 (0.8-8.3)
Elite controllers (identified by SCOPE cohort)	31 (89)	48.4 (30.2-66.9)
Treated subjects (no previous treatment interruption and treated for at least 3 months)	113 (185)	76.1 (67.2-83.6)
By time from infection to treatment (years)		
[0,0.5)	53 (90)	92.5 (81.8-97.9)
≥0.5	53 (88)	56.6 (42.3-70.2)
Low viral load (<75 copies/ml at draw)	154 (273)	68.5 (60.5-75.7)
Low CD4+ T cell count (<200 cells/μl at draw)	124 (214)	2.4 (0.5-6.9)

Figure 6: Estimated proportions of 'recent' results in various sets of specimens drawn from subjects infected for greater than T=2 years

Table 8: Estimated assay characteristics (and 95% confidence intervals), for ARV-naïve subjects and excluding SCOPE elite controllers, by subtype

Assay characteristics are estimated for $T = 2$ years and a context in which an HIV viral lysate-based Western blot assay is used to identify HIV-positive subjects in the incidence study.

	Number of subjects (number of data points)	Estimated assay characteristics (95% CI)
MDRI in days¹		
All specimens	400 (1032)	306 (274-338)
Subtype B	90 (246)	232 (173-299)
Subtype C	181 (454)	265 (221-311)
Subtype D	38 (131)	264 (190-339)
Subtype A1	80 (166)	473 (387-560)
FRR as %²		
All specimens	316 (665)	9.7 (6.6-13.5)
Subtype B	190 (388)	4.7 (2.2-8.8)
Subtype C	75 (144)	8.7 (3.4-17.5)
Subtype D	11 (18)	18.2 (2.3-51.8)
Subtype A1	37 (106)	35.1 (20.2-52.5)

¹ In a test for pairwise differences in MDRI by subtype, using a z-test, the following pairs provided p-values below 0.05: A1&B, A1&C, A1&D. Estimated standard deviations of the MDRI estimators are used as proxies for true values, and therefore tests are anticonservative (particularly when sample sizes are small).

² In a test for pairwise differences in FRRs by subtype, using the Fisher-Boschloo test [17], the following pairs provided p-values below 0.05: A1&B, A1&C.

Lastly, Figures 7 and 8 summarise the assay measurements for the reproducibility of CEPHIA control specimens included in the evaluation. 75 of the uniquely-labelled 2,500 specimens on the evaluation panel represent 25 aliquots of each of three underlying specimens. The reproducibility of measurements for these 3 'blinded' controls is described in Figure 7. Three labelled internal quality controls were also tested regularly during evaluation panel testing, for confirmation of stability of the assay. The results for these controls are summarised in Figure 8. LS-Vitros quantitative results appear to be highly reproducible.

Figure 7: Reproducibility of CEPHIA *unlabelled* controls

The box-and-whisker plots (top) provide percentiles of the 25 measurements for each of the three blinded reproducibility specimens (labelled A, B and C in the figure only). The central 50% and median of measurements are captured by the box and dividing line respectively, and whiskers and markers capture remaining measurements and outliers respectively. The 'recent'/'non-recent' threshold is shown by the vertical solid line. The observed reproducibility statistics (mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation) of measurements are also tabulated (bottom).

* One outlier was discarded.

Summary of measurements				
Specimen identifier	Number of measurements	Mean (S/C)	Standard deviation (S/C)	Coefficient of variation (%)
A*	24	14.1	1.0	7
B	25	53.9	2.1	4
C	25	65.8	2.1	3

Figure 8: Reproducibility of CEPHIA labelled controls

The box-and-whisker plots (top) provide percentiles of the 24 measurements for each of the three labelled quality control specimens (labelled D, E and F in the figure only). The central 50% and median of measurements are captured by the box and dividing line respectively, and whiskers and markers capture remaining measurements and outliers respectively. The 'recent'/'non-recent' threshold is shown by the vertical solid line. The observed reproducibility statistics (mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation) of measurements are also tabulated (bottom).

Summary of measurements				
Specimen identifier	Number of measurements	Mean (S/C)	Standard deviation (S/C)	Coefficient of variation (%)
D	24	2.3	0.2	9
E	24	10.0	0.7	7
F	24	52.0	2.6	5

Conclusion/Recommendations

Ortho Less Sensitive (LS)-VITROS ECI

The following conclusions relate to the assay in its off-label modified format and do not relate to its licensed diagnostic performance:

- 1) Given its performance in relation to the Target Product Profile and to other candidate assays this assay is not recommended for use in cross-sectional incidence assays.
- 2) In particular this assay is not a promising candidate assay due to its high False Recent Rate of 10%.
- 3) The CEPHIA group do not believe that varying of thresholds or use of currently described RITA algorithms will improve the performance of this assay to an acceptable level.
- 4) The automated nature of this assay means that there are considerable infrastructure demands for resource limited settings. However, the assay is extremely reproducible and the platform may be useful for other laboratory testing.
- 5) A number of groups are looking at these modified assays for a number of different purposes and alternative target product profiles are being prepared. The use of this assay for against other TPPs will be assessed when these are published.

Technical Appraisal

Assay Kits and Reagents

The VITROS HIV-1/2 assay requires storage at 2-8°C. The kit contains 1 x 100 tests per kit. Each run requires diluent buffer, calibrator, controls, reagent packs, signal reagent and prepared wash buffer. Controls are run once a day. Multiple kits of the same lot of reagent pack can be loaded on the machine at the same time and stored in the 4°C storage unit.

Prior to running a new assay lot, a calibration must be performed. The calibration is valid for all subsequent tests using that particular lot number; it is not time limited. The mean of the triplicate RLU of the calibrator is calculated to provide the cut-off (CO) for the reagent lot. It is recommended that the four HIV kit controls are run at least once every 24 hours that the test is in use. The kit insert details the acceptable ranges for each control.

The VITROS ECI is a fully automated analyser; all processing steps are performed on the instrument. However, the use of the less sensitive method on the analyser does require a much more involved operator interaction during assay preparation to ensure the assay is run correctly. The analyser requires a stable electricity supply.

The analyser requires daily maintenance where the analyser completes the program automatically. Weekly maintenance is also required in which the sample, reagent and wash probes, and air filters are cleaned. The machine is left on and will perform periodic system flushing when not in use.

The system may have the capability of performing on-board dilution if the assay has been found to perform well for calculating incidence in populations. All reagents can be kept on board as there are storage conditions that are appropriate for each reagent from the assay.

For the clinical test results are expressed as sample RLU/cut-off (S/CO). Singlet 1 ODn of a specimen is < 30 the specimen must be retested in duplicate. The final Confirmatory Result will be a Mean S/C of the Duplicate results.

Exclusion criteria

The cut-off of the Vitros assay is 1.0.

Assay Preparation

Sample Worklist and labels:

Requires preparation of excel work list of Sample IDs and Controls from the CEPHIA specimen repository, then creation of daily worksheets from CEPHIA Document 019C_LS-VITROS Data. The sample carousel is loaded with the diluted samples in sample cups; the IDs for the samples are entered into the software for the corresponding seats on the carousel.

Sample Preparation:

The sample dilutions are prepared in sample dilution tubes off-board and then loaded into sample cups. This is then entered into the software and the samples are placed on the machine. This requires a large amount of concentration and accuracy from the operator to ensure the correct sample is added to the correct sample cup.

Addition of samples to sample cups can cause bubbles to appear. These bubbles must be removed carefully prior to testing on the analyser as they will cause an error in the probe and therefore the failure of the sample test. This requires operator intervention and time.

Associated documentation

The older system that was used for this evaluation did not have capacity for transferring data electronically and so the results were manually entered into an excel spreadsheet. There could be potential for errors here.

Kit inserts: There are no kit inserts. Everything is performed on board by the ECI and the protocol for this process is set up by the protocol card that is provided for every reagent pack lot.

Software updates should be conveyed to the laboratory by the manufacturer during the purchase of reagents.

Technical Conclusions

The VITROS ECI analyser is an expensive, specialised piece of equipment that most laboratories would not have but is available for purchase or rent. It requires a specialist operator/superuser to rectify any problems. The automation of the system allows for easy use and precision. Once training has been provided operation of the system is straightforward but sometimes difficult to use if there are ERROR codes during assay. The evaluation was performed on an older machine and had 3 major errors during the performance of this evaluation. This required manufacturer technical support to attend to fix the machine. The use of the LS-VITROS method on the analyser does require a much more involved operator interaction to ensure the assay is run correctly. The most time-consuming aspect of the LS-VITROS assay is the assay preparation and typing the IDs into the system. The labelling of sample cups requires a high level of concentration to prevent error. However, once a reliable system of assay preparation has been established a large number of samples can be tested in a short space of time making the LS-Vitros method an efficient test for large-scale testing.

The reliability of accompanying documents e.g. spreadsheets, data files, QC charts, is vital to the performance of the assay. The operator must be vigilant in transferring data and maintaining these documents to ensure information is correct. The data sheets were prepared by the developer and are not commercially available. If adopted it is critical that the user develop a system for ensuring appropriate data handling safeguards are in place.

The result reflects the signal intensity for both HIV-1+2 antibodies therefore care should be taken to ensure that the specimen is only HIV-1 positive. The assay was found to have a high false recent rate with a long duration of recency. It would not be appropriate for using in a cross sectional calculation of incidence. Being a modified commercial assay the responsibility for validation of the modified procedure lies with the user and this may be difficult to achieve should the manufacturer make any changes to the assay

Advantages

The assay takes approximately 50 minutes from start to finish and so could feasibly be performed in real time if there was a Diagnostic System in the clinic lab.

Reproducibility is exceptional and was consistently around 5%, something that was not seen for most of the other assays.

CEPHIA Testing Process:

Evaluation Panel: Singlet-Confirmatory

- Singlet 1
- Confirmatory 1 and Confirmatory 2

Target Product Profile performance

Specification	Acceptable Performance	Ideal Performance	How does Ortho-LS fit?
Intended Use	<i>Population-based incidence estimate</i>	<i>Population-based incidence estimate, prevention-trial planning, community-level prevention intervention studies</i>	<i>Although it has a long recency period, it has a high false recent rate. Not appropriate for solo use in incidence calculations</i>
Target Population	<i>Specific to clade</i>	<i>All clades</i>	<i>Performance of non-clade B is worse than clade B. Not appropriate for international population based incidence surveillance.</i>
False Recent Rate (FRR)	<i>Confidently measured to be less than 2% in different populations (with different clades, epidemic phases, treatment coverage etc)</i>	<i>0% in all population (No evidence of false-recent classifications).</i>	Failed - 9.7% (6.6-13.5)
Mean Duration	<i>4 months (95% CI, +/- 0.2)</i>	<i>1 year (95% CI, +/- 0.2)</i>	<i>Acceptable -285 days</i>
Algorithm	<i>Included in a RITA</i>	<i>None required</i>	<i>CEPHIA does not recommend use of this assay</i>
Analyte	<i>Any</i>	<i>Any</i>	<i>ENV and p24 proteins.</i>
Sample Type	<i>Frozen serum, frozen plasma</i>	<i>Frozen serum or plasma , dried blood spots (or other easily obtained and stored sample)</i>	<i>Acceptable -Frozen serum or plasma.</i>

Sample Volume	1 mL	10 uL or fingerstick	Acceptable -60uL total.
Infrastructure requirements	Centralized laboratory facility (clean water and electricity available)	None (all reagents and necessary materials to run assay are in self-contained kit)	Centralized Lab.
Storage/Shipping Conditions	4-25 °C	Ambient temperature	2-8°C
Incubation Temperature	4-25 °C	Ambient temperature	On-board incubator.
Shelf Life	9 months	>18 months	Acceptable - 12 months
Training	Laboratory technician can be proficient with one week's training based on proficiency testing	Minimal training would allow any health worker to conduct the assay	Acceptable - Laboratory technician can be proficient with one week's training based on proficiency testing
Regulatory Pathway	GMP or ISO 13485 or equivalent, and/or approval by national governing body	FDA and equivalents	The clinical diagnostic system is FDA cleared; the modified version of the assay has not been approved by any agency.

Acknowledgements

Funding for this project was provided by the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation (grant OPP1017716).

The authors acknowledge with thanks David Matten for database support; and the CEPHIA steering group for their advice and suggestions on the data outputs of this work. Ortho Clinical Diagnostics provided assay kit and reagents free of charge for this evaluation.

The *Consortium for the Evaluation and Performance of HIV Incidence Assays* (CEPHIA) is comprised of the authors and: Tom Quinn, Oliver Laeyendecker (Johns Hopkins University); David Burns (National Institutes of Health); Jesus Maria Garcia Calleja (World Health Organization); Tim Hallett (Imperial College London); Sherry Michele Owen, Bharat Parekh, Connie Sexton (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention); Anatoli Kamali (International AIDS Vaccine Initiative); David Matten, Hilmarié Brand (South African Centre for Epidemiological Modelling and Analysis); Kara Marson (University of California, San Francisco); Megha Mittal (Public Health England); Mila Lebedeva, Dylan Hampton (Blood Systems Research Institute); Lisa Loeb, Kara Marson (The Options Study – University of California, San Francisco); Steven G Deeks, Rebecca Hoh (The SCOPE Study – University of California, San Francisco); Zelinda Bartolomei, Natalia Cerqueira (The AMPLIAR Cohort – University of São Paulo); Breno Santos, Kellin Zabtowski, Rita de Cassia Alves Lira (The AMPLIAR Cohort – Grupo Hospital Conceição); Rosa Dea Sperhacke, Leonardo R Motta, Machline Paganella (The AMPLIAR Cohort – Universidade Caxias Do Sul); Helena Tomiyama, Claudia Tomiyama, Priscilla Costa, Maria A Nunes, Gisele Reis, Mariana M Sauer, Natalia Cerqueira, Zelinda Nakagawa, Lilian Ferrari, Ana P Amaral, Karine Milani (The São Paulo Cohort – University of São Paulo, Brazil); Salim S Abdool Karim, Quarraisha Abdool Karim, Thumbi Ndungu, Nigel Garret, Nelisile Majola, Natasha Samsunder (CAPRISA, University of Kwazulu-Natal); Denise Nanche (The GAMA Study – Barcelona Centre for International Health Research); Inácio Mandomando, Eusebio V Macete (The GAMA Study – Fundacao Manhica); Jorge Sanchez, Javier Lama (SABES Cohort – Asociación Civil Impacta Salud y Educación (IMPACTA)); Ann Duerr (The Fred Hutchinson Cancer Research Center); Maria R Capobianchi (National Institute for Infectious Diseases "L. Spallanzani", Rome); Barbara Suligoi (Istituto Superiore di Sanità, Rome); Susan Stramer (American Red Cross); Phillip Williamson (Creative Testing Solutions / Blood Systems Research Institute); Marion Vermeulen (South African National Blood Service); and Ester Sabino (Hemocentro do Sao Paolo).

References

1. (2014) CEPHIA Website. <http://www.incidence-estimation.org/page/cephia-overview>
2. Kassanjee R, Murphy G, Busch MP, Pilcher CD, McKinney E, Keating S, *et al.* The Performance of Candidate Assays to Detect Recent HIV Infection for Cross-Sectional Incidence Estimation: An Independent, Comparative Evaluation. Poster 1056 / abstract X-168 at the *20th Conference on Retroviruses and Opportunistic Infections*, Atlanta, GA, 3-6 March 2013
3. Kassanjee R, Pilcher CD, Keating SM, Facente SN, McKinney E, *et al.* (2014) Independent assessment of candidate HIV incidence assays on specimens in the CEPHIA repository. *Aids* 28: 2439-2449.
4. Brookmeyer R, Quinn TC (1995) Estimation of current human immunodeficiency virus incidence rates from a cross-sectional survey using early diagnostic tests. *Am J Epidemiol* 141: 166-172.
5. Kassanjee R, McWalter TA, Barnighausen T, Welte A (2012) A new general biomarker-based incidence estimator. *Epidemiology* 23: 721-728.
6. Fiebig EW, Wright DJ, Rawal BD, Garrett PE, Schumacher RT, *et al.* (2003) Dynamics of HIV viremia and antibody seroconversion in plasma donors: implications for diagnosis and staging of primary HIV infection. *Aids* 17: 1871-1879.
7. Lee HY, Giorgi EE, Keele BF, Gaschen B, Athreya GS, *et al.* (2009) Modeling sequence evolution in acute HIV-1 infection. *J Theor Biol* 261: 341-360.
8. Schacker T, Collier AC, Hughes J, Shea T, Corey L (1996) Clinical and epidemiologic features of primary HIV infection. *Ann Intern Med* 125: 257-264.
9. Borrow P, Lewicki H, Wei X, Horwitz MS, Peffer N, *et al.* (1997) Antiviral pressure exerted by HIV-1-specific cytotoxic T lymphocytes (CTLs) during primary infection demonstrated by rapid selection of CTL escape virus. *Nat Med* 3: 205-211.
10. Lindback S, Karlsson AC, Mittler J, Blaxhult A, Carlsson M, *et al.* (2000) Viral dynamics in primary HIV-1 infection. Karolinska Institutet Primary HIV Infection Study Group. *Aids* 14: 2283-2291.
11. Pilcher CD, Eron JJ, Jr., Vemazza PL, Battegay M, Harr T, *et al.* (2001) Sexual transmission during the incubation period of primary HIV infection. *Jama* 286: 1713-1714.
12. (2014) HIV Modelling Consortium Work Package on Characterisation of Tests for Recent Infection. . <http://www.hivmodelling.org/projects/incidence-estimation>.
13. Brookmeyer R, Konikoff J, Laeyendecker O, Eshleman SH (2013) Estimation of HIV incidence using multiple biomarkers. *Am J Epidemiol* 177: 264-272.
14. Efron B, Tibshirani RJ (1993) *An Introduction to the Bootstrap (Monographs on Statistics and Applied Probability 57)*. New York: Chapman & Hall / CRC.
- 15.. Agresti A, Coull BA (1998) Approximate is better than "exact" for interval estimation of binomial proportions. *The American Statistician* 52: 119-126.
16. Masciotra S, McDougal JS, Feldman J, Sprinkle P, Wesolowski L, *et al.* (2011) Evaluation of an alternative HIV diagnostic algorithm using specimens from seroconversion panels and persons with established HIV infections. *J Clin Virol* 52 Suppl 1: S17-22.
17. Mehrotra DV, Chan IS, Berger RL (2003) A cautionary note on exact unconditional inference for a difference between two independent binomial proportions. *Biometrics* 59: 441-450.

Appendix

1. Evaluation Protocol

Background

The Ortho Less-Sensitive VITROS Assay is to be evaluated by the CEPHIA group as part of The Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation funded project, 'Development of specimen repository and evaluation of assays for identification of recent HIV infection and estimation of HIV incidence'. The group will also undertake evaluations of a number of other available assays for HIV recency. Each of these evaluations will have their own CEPHIA Book Report available.

Evaluation Purpose

To advance the understanding of currently available assays that can identify recent HIV infection; to better describe the duration of the infection state in which they identify recent infection; and to determine the rate at which they misclassify specimens as from recent infections

Conduct of the evaluation

All CEPHIA evaluations are conducted following the **CEPHIA Quality Management Strategy** (Document 002) which details the quality planning, quality control and quality assurance in place at Public Health England (PHE), Microbiology Services (MS), Colindale and the collaborating organisations of Blood Systems Research Institute (BSRI), San Francisco, University of California, San Francisco (UCSF) and South African Centre for Epidemiological Modelling and Analysis (SACEMA), University of Stellenbosch, South Africa, to ensure the delivery of the Bill & Melinda Gates Funded (BMGF) Project.

The main objectives of the quality strategy are: to define the quality requirements, how they are to be met, who is responsible for meeting requirements, and helping to align quality strategies between the multiple sites involved in the overall project.

The CEPHIA Quality Management Strategy details the quality procedures in place for all CEPHIA evaluations with regards to Project Organisation – roles, responsibilities and personnel, Facilities, Equipment, Standard Operating procedures (SOP), Worksheets, Plans, Sub-contracting, Conduct of project, Computer systems, Safety and risk, Method validations, Results, Reporting process and templates, Repeat analysis, Retention of data/specimens, Confidentiality. The quality strategy will be based on UK CPA standards and also MHRA Good Clinical Practise 'Guidance on the maintenance of regulatory compliance in laboratories that perform the analysis or evaluation of clinical trial samples', it will also refer to local site regulations and standards.

- **The assay under evaluation will be tested in exactly the manner laid down in the manufacturer/developers instructions.**
- **Evaluator(s) will strictly adhere to the quality requirements laid out in the CEPHIA Quality Management Strategy.**
- **Prior to beginning the evaluation, the manufacturer/developer will be invited, if they so wish, to provide training to the evaluator in the use of the assay kit and equipment and to satisfy themselves that the evaluator(s) is trained sufficiently.**

Specimen Handling

A main objective of this project is to compile large-volume, standardized sample sets appropriate for comparative evaluation of tests for recent HIV infection in an accessible central repository.

These serum samples will be sourced by the CEPHIA team at University of California San Francisco (UCSF), blinded so evaluator(s) will not know the expected results, then aliquotted at the central repository (Blood Systems Research Institute, San Francisco) and shipped to the relevant test site.

Documentation

The CEPHIA group have compiled a folder of documents relating to the plans, procedures and protocols required for the high quality performance and completion of the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation funded project. These documents are securely stored in a management-only access folder until the project end. Some relevant documents are available for public reading on the CEPHIA website at <http://www.incidence-estimation.com/archivesuploads/index/NAME/11>

Other aspects of the evaluation

Technical appraisal of the procedure, assay kit and equipment required for the performance of the assay. This may include ease of use, reliability, packaging, clarity, health and safety considerations.

Discordant results

A discrepancy may arise at the test site and should be investigated by an appropriately trained person prior to data being verified and reported for analysis. If a discrepancy is identified at the analysis site (SACEMA), a report detailing the error will be sent to the test site for further investigation.

Analysis of results and evaluation report

The raw laboratory data is compiled and verified at the test site. It is stored electronically in a Data Table formatted as described in the *CEPHIA Data Processing Protocol: Data Flow, Recording and Standard Formats*.

Verified and formatted data is e-mailed to the analysis site (SACEMA). The analysis site will run data through checks and generate a report prior to using the data for analysis. Data analysis will be reported in the CEPHIA Book. The manufacturer/developer of the assay concerned will be given the opportunity to comment on results prior to any publishing of data.

2. CEPHIA Project Management Contact Details

1. PHE – Public Health England, Microbiology Services, Colindale, London, UK
2. BSRI - Blood Systems Research Institute, San Francisco
3. UCSF – University of California, San Francisco
4. SACEMA - South African Centre for Epidemiological Modelling and Analysis

Project Management Team:				
Gary Murphy	PHE	London, UK	Assay evaluation	gary.murphy@phe.gov.uk
Mike Busch	BSRI	San Francisco	Specimen collection / Assay evaluation	mbusch@bloodsystems.org
Chris Pilcher	UCSF	San Francisco	Specimen collection	cpilcher@php.ucsf.edu
Alex Welte	SACEMA	South Africa	Statistical analysis	alexwelte@sun.ac.za
Site Project Managers:				
Elaine McKinney	PHE	London, UK	Assay evaluation	Elaine.mckinney@phe.gov.uk
Sheila Keating	BSRI	San Francisco	Specimen collection / Assay evaluation	skeating@bloodsystems.org
Shelley Facente	UCSF	San Francisco	Specimen collection	facentes@php.ucsf.edu
Reshma Kassanjee	SACEMA	South Africa	Statistical analysis	rkassanjee@sun.ac.za

Manufacturer's comments

A copy of this report was made available to the manufacturer and the following comment was received:

These reports are very well written. I have no additional comments.

Enquiries

General enquiries on this evaluation report should be directed to Dr Gary Murphy at Public Health England, London, UK

Tel: 0044-208-327-6935

E-mail: Gary.murphy@phe.gov.uk